

Step 1 – Install Anki

Download and install Anki: <https://apps.ankiweb.net/>

After installing, you should see a blank Anki similar to the example on the right:

Step 2 – Upload pre-made deck

Download the NYU Grossman School of Medicine Anki deck (extension .apkg);

Double-click the .apkg file. You will see a note about contents, just hit close.

You will now have the template deck.

Step 3 – Browse cards

- On the upper bar, click on browse. This will open the “back-end” of the Anki cards.
- Select one deck.
- For each *drug class + examples*, 3 cards are produced: Mechanisms of Action, Indication, and Major Side Effects.
- Click on **preview** to see what that particular card looks like
- Changing the content in the different fields will change the content of the cards
- You can also delete any cards by right-clicking on the particular card you wish to delete.

Step 4 – Create your own deck

- Back to “decks”
- Click on “create deck”
- Name your deck and hit OK

Step 5 – create your cards

- Click on the deck where you want to add cards to;
- Click on **Add**

Step 6 – Getting familiar with the interface

Anki will open a window for you to add content.

- You can choose the **“note type”** which determines the layout of your cards, and how many cards will be produced from the content you input in this window
- By default, you will see the last note type you used (in this case, a NYUGSoM card).
- You can also add those cards to a different deck by clicking on **deck**.

Step 7 – create a pharmacology card

- Add text
- Click on **cards** to see a preview
- Preview the front of the card
- Preview the back of the card
- Click on **card type** to toggle between the 3 cards that will be created
- Close the preview and click on **ADD**

Step 8 – Export your new deck

- After creating cards, you can export your deck and share with anyone
- Click on the gear icon and select **export**

